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Spontaneous fibroadenoma in a young adult female rat: A case report

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Abstract

A 14 week old female Wistar rat, developed a gradually enlarging mass on the ventral side of the thoracic region. Based on clinical examinations, a tumor was suspected as part of the differential diagnosis, and the rat was surgically treated under general anesthesia. Histopathological examination revealed a fibroadenoma located in the mammary region. Hematological analysis was used to monitor any potential adverse effects of the tumor and the surgical procedure which involved tumor excision on the general health status of the patient. The rat recovered well without any complications. Fibroadenoma is a common benign tumor in older rats but is rarely observed in young adult, making this case a valuable contribution to understanding early-onset mammary fibroadenomas in rodents.

Keywords: *Benign tumor, female, mammary gland, prolactin, wistar strain*

1. Introduction

Predisposing factors for tumor development in rats include genetic predisposition, diet, environmental influences, physiological and hormonal status, and especially elevated levels of prolactin.¹ In general, rats are prone to a high incidence of tumors, most of which are benign in nature.^{2,3}

Fibroadenoma (FA) is a benign breast tumor characterized by distinctive and unique proliferation of fibrovascular stroma and glandular epithelial components.⁴ Mammary gland FA is the most common subcutaneous tumor in rats. Due to the extensive distribution of mammary gland tissue in rats, mammary tumors can occur anywhere from the cervical to the inguinal region.⁵

In rats, this benign tumor may grow under the influence of increased plasma prolactin concentrations during estrus.⁶ There are also reports indicating that prolactin secretion may increase under other circumstances, such as reduced dopamine release from the pituitary gland in older rats, persistently low progesterone levels, or disruption of ovulation in female rats.⁷

FA occurs with high frequency in rats, most commonly in females.^{6,8} According to a long-term retrospective study by Vergneau-Grosset et al.⁹, the most frequently diagnosed tumor in pet rats was mammary gland FA, ac-

counting for 53% of cases, while Poteracki and Walsh¹⁰ reported a prevalence of 36.1%.

This type of tumor can also occur in male rats, although it is significantly rarer, as the growth of mammary glands is primarily stimulated by prolactin secretion and indirectly influenced by estrogen.^{11,12} Generally, FA in Wistar rats tends to occur more frequently between 31 and 36 months of age and is rare in Wistar and other rat strains younger than 26 weeks.¹³

We present a rare case of spontaneous FA located in mammary, in a young adult female rat aged 14 weeks. The aim of this report is to describe the case of FA in a younger adult female rat, localized in the *regio thoracic*, and its surgical treatment approach.

2. Case Presentation

In the laboratory rat breeding facility of the Veterinary Faculty at the University of Sarajevo, an abnormal formation was clinically diagnosed in the ventral part of the thorax, extending into the right axillary region, in an intact 14-week-old female Wistar rat weighing 265 grams (Figure 1). The rat had not given birth, was not pregnant, and was housed individually in a cage with a temperature of 22 °C, air humidity of 60%, and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. She consumed standard conventional rat feed.

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Figure 1. Clinical examination of an adult female rat showing a visible abnormal formation in the *regio thoracic*.

In addition to slightly impaired use of the right forelimb during movement, the rat showed no other signs of general health disturbance. The mass located on the ventral side of the thorax was initially considered, in differential diagnosis, to resemble an abscess. Upon palpation, the mass was mobile, smooth, and had a rubbery consistency, and the animal did not show signs of pain during the examination.

An attempt to aspirate the mass using a standard needle and syringe typically used for intramuscular applications confirmed that the formation was not an abscess. Surgical excision of the mass was indicated, and the rat was anesthetized using 5 mg/kg of 2% xylazine hydrochloride (2% Xylazin, CpPharma, Bergdorf, Germany) and 50 mg/kg of ketamine hydrochloride (International B.V., Netherlands), administered intramuscularly.

Following standard surgical protocols and principles, the rat was positioned in dorsal recumbency with the mass facing upward. The fur covering was removed and the surgical area was disinfected. An elliptical incision was made around the mass, which was then resected from the surrounding tissue using blunt dissection. A slightly increased amount of bleeding during the procedure was controlled by ligation.

Muscle and subcutaneous tissue were sutured separately using a continuous suture technique with Polyglactin 910 (No. 2.0), and the skin was closed with interrupted sutures using Ethicon (No. 2.0). Ultimately, a tumorous formation weighing 16 grams was excised (Figure 2).

Immediately after the surgical procedure, a peripheral blood sample of approximately 2 mL was collected for standard hematological analysis via tail vein puncture into 3 mL EDTA vacutainers. The puncture site was disinfected beforehand using standard disinfectants for hematological sampling.

Postoperatively, the patient was housed in a separate cage with bedding made of conifer wood shavings. Pellet food and water were provided ad libitum. The surgical wound area was treated with chlorine dioxide (ClO₂) at a concentration of 120 ppm (ITR d.o.o., Bosnia and Herzegovina) in spray form, twice daily for seven days,

to prevent potential secondary infections. Sutures were removed on the twelfth day after surgery. The postoperative period passed successfully without any complications.

Hematological parameters were obtained using the automated hematology analyzer Mindray BC-20S. Leukocyte cell types were differentiated, and numerical values were expressed as percentages after analyzing 1000 cells, using a Motic Type 102 M light binocular microscope at 1000× magnification.

The tumorous tissue sample was fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin, dehydrated, embedded in paraffin, sectioned at 5 μm, mounted on a glass slide, and stained with hematoxylin and eosin for microscopic evaluation.

Figure 2. Excised tumorous formation after surgical procedure.

Table 1. Hematological parameters of the rat after surgical procedure.

Parameters	Unit	Results	Ref - Ranges
WBC	10 ⁹ /L	6.23	1.90-13.80
Lymphocytes	%	79	75.8-92.9
Neutrophils	%	18	3,5-18.7
Monocytes	%	2	0.5-3.4
Basophils	%	0	0.2-0.6
Acidophiles	%	1	0.0-0.6
RBC	10 ¹² /L	7.48	4.82-9.80
HGB	g/L	139	110-170
HCT	%	42.6	27-46
MCV	fL	57	50-67
MCH	pg	18.5	16-25
MCHC	g/L	325	310-390
RDW-CV	%	1.35	1.1-1.5
RDW-SD	fL	29.4	25-40
PLT	10 ⁹ /L	1616	250-1400
MPV	fL	6.5	5.1-8.2
PDW	f/L	15.1	12-17.5
PCT	ml/L	10.49	2-8.2
P-LCC	10 ⁹ /L	532	100-580
P-LCR	%	0,33	0,22-0,57

Figure 3. a: Nodular appearance of a fibroadenoma located in the mammary region composed of fibrous stroma surrounding and compressing proliferated ducts, magnification 50×. b: Cellular fibrous stroma of a fibroadenoma located in the mammary region with proliferated ducts lined by a bilayered epithelium consisting of luminal cuboidal epithelial cells and basal myoepithelial cells, magnification 200×.

3. Discussion and Conclusion

Historically, rats with mammary gland tumors have not undergone extensive diagnostic testing, and excised tumors are often not histologically analyzed based on the assumption that the mass is most likely benign in nature.¹⁴ Overall, the consensus within the veterinary community appears to be that surgical excision of a mass in rats is beneficial, provided the affected animal is considered a suitable candidate for anesthesia.^{9,14}

In our case, the excised tumor underwent histopathological examination, which revealed proliferation of fibrous stroma and myoepithelial cells, with a pronounced nodular appearance, clearly and unequivocally confirming the diagnosis of a FA located in the mammary region. Understanding the histopathology of FA is a key aspect in establishing an accurate diagnosis and making informed decisions regarding treatment of the affected animal.

FA is typically found in the axillary regions, along the broader abdominal belt, or in the inguinal area.^{13,15} In our case, the tumor was located on the ventral side of the thorax, fully encompassing the right axillary region. It was treated by surgical excision, which corresponds entirely with the case report by Parmar et al.³, where an adult female rat was also diagnosed with FA in the thoracic region and underwent surgical removal.

Similar cases of FA have also been reported by Shafiuza-ma et al.¹⁶, Kathio and Tunio¹⁷, and Millán et al.¹³, where the tumor was located on the ventral abdomen, the left lateral thoracic region, and the inguinal area, respectively, and in all cases surgical excision was performed. The operated rats in those reports were significantly older compared to the subject in our case.

Hematological parameters related to the total number of erythrocytes (RBC), red blood cell distribution width (RDW-CV and RDW-SD), as well as mean corpuscular volume (MCV), hematocrit (HCT), hemoglobin content (HGB), and other erythrocyte indices such as mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH) and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC) remained within reference physiological ranges. An increased platelet count above the upper physiological limit was observed. Evident thrombocytosis may be associated with hemorrhage that occurred during the surgical procedure and blood loss caused by tail vein puncture for hematologi-

cal testing.

It is important to note that rats, like other small rodents, are highly sensitive to blood loss, and even minor losses can pose a life-threatening risk.¹⁸ Therefore, the hemorrhage caused by disruption of small blood vessels during surgery may trigger a physiological adaptation in the patient, involving mobilization of platelets from the spleen and lungs, accelerated megakaryocytopoiesis in the bone marrow, fragmentation of mature megakaryocyte cytoplasm, and rapid release of platelets into peripheral blood, resulting in an elevated platelet count above the normal range.

The increased total platelet count corresponded with a higher value of total platelet volume in the blood (PCT). Other platelet-related parameters, such as mean platelet volume (MPV) and platelet distribution width (PDW), which describe variability and activity of larger platelets, remained within physiological limits. The same applies to platelet large cell count (P-LCC) and platelet large cell ratio (P-LCR), which reflect the total number and condition of large platelets. The total leukocyte count (WBC), as well as all leukocyte subtypes, remained within physiological ranges, indicating the absence of active inflammatory processes in the patient.

If a benign tumor is left untreated, it may continue to grow and reach up to half the body weight of the affected animal.³ Predisposing factors such as genetic, physiological, and hormonal status, as well as diet, may further negatively influence the development of additional complications in cases where the tumor is not treated, ultimately accelerating a fatal outcome.

Following surgical removal of tumorous masses in rats, the prognosis is favorable, and surgery remains the only viable treatment option for such patients. The benefits of surgical excision of FA include ruling out other malignant tumor variants through differential diagnosis, improving the animal's quality of life and mobility, and preventing the development of secondary ulceration, which would otherwise necessitate euthanasia. However, it should be noted that although tumors can be successfully removed, they have a tendency to recur.

A limitation of this report is the absence of immunohistochemical confirmation (IHC), which would further substantiate the diagnosis. Nevertheless, the microscopic architecture characterized by fibrous stroma proli-

feration surrounding bilayered glandular ducts supports the histopathological identification of fibroadenoma.

Ethical approval

None

Authors contribution

MK, NKD, DŽHA, EČ: Research, writing-original draft & review; AB, NK, AL, AB: planing, article scanning

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest associated with this re-search publication, according to the authors.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request

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